

Effect of three-orifice baffles orientation on the flow and thermal-hydraulic performance: experimental analysis for net and oscillatory flows

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Abstract

Three-orifice baffles equally spaced along a circular tube are investigated as a means for heat transfer enhancement under net, oscillatory and compound flows. An unprecedented, systematic analysis of the of the relative orientation of consecutive baffles -aligned or opposed- is accomplished to assess the changes induced on the flow structure and their impact on the thermal-hydraulic performance. The results cover the Nusselt number, the net and oscillatory friction factors and the instantaneous velocity fields using PIV in an experimental campaign with a 32 mm tube diameter. The study is conducted in the range of net Reynolds numbers $50 < Re_n < 1000$ and oscillatory Reynolds numbers $0 < Re_{osc} < 750$, for a dimensionless amplitude $x_0/D = 0.5$ and $Pr = 65$. In absence of oscillatory flow, opposed baffles advance the transition to turbulence from $Re_n = 100$ to 50, increasing the net friction factor (40%) for $Re_n > 50$ and the Nusselt number (maximum of 27%) for $Re_n < 150$. When an oscillatory flow is applied, augmentations caused by opposed baffles are only observed for $Re_n < 150$ and $Re_{osc} < 150$. Above $Re_n, Re_{osc} > 150$, opposed baffles are not recommended for the promotion of heat transfer, owing to friction penalties. However, the chaotic mixing and lack of short-circuiting between baffles observed with flow velocimetry over a wide range of operational conditions point out the interest of this configuration to achieve plug flow.

Keywords: Oscillatory baffled reactors, Heat transfer enhancement, Compound techniques, Oscillatory flow, Particle Image Velocimetry

1	Nomenclature	16	q'' heat flux, W/m ²
2	C Propylene glycol weight concentration, %	17	Q_{losses} heat losses, W
3	c_p specific heat (J/(kg·K))	18	S open area (-), $(n \cdot d/D)^2$
4	d orifice diameter (m)	19	T temperature (°C)
5	D tube inner diameter (m)	20	u velocity vector (m/s)
6	f oscillation frequency (Hz)	21	U instantaneous bulk flow velocity (m/s), based on D
7	h heat transfer coefficient (W/(m ² ·K))	22	U_n bulk velocity of the net flow (m/s), based on D
8	I electric current (A)	23	V voltage (V)
9	k thermal conductivity (W/(m·K))	24	x axial distance from the start of the heated area (m)
10	l cell length (m)	25	x_0 oscillation amplitude, center to peak (m)
11	L_h heated length (m)	26	<u>Greek symbols</u>
12	L_p distance between pressure ports (m)	27	β coefficient of volumetric thermal expansion (1/K)
13	L_v baffled tube length in PIV facility (m)	28	μ dynamic viscosity (kg/(m·s))
14	$L_{e,v}$ entry-outlet length in PIV facility (m)	29	ν kinematic viscosity (m ² /s)
15	\dot{m} mass flow rate (kg/s)	30	ρ fluid density (kg/m ³)

31 θ oscillation phase angle ($^\circ$)
32 Δt time step between consecutive images (s)
33 Δp_n net pressure drop (Pa)
34 Δp_{max} amplitude of the oscillating pressure drop (Pa)
35 Subscripts
36 b bulk
37 in inlet of the test section
38 j section number
39 k circumferential position number
40 wi inner wall
41 Dimensionless groups
42 f_n net Fanning friction factor, $\frac{\Delta p_n}{2\rho U_n^2} \frac{D}{L_p}$
43 f_n oscillatory Fanning friction factor, $\frac{\Delta p_{max}}{2\rho (2\pi f x_0)^2} \frac{D}{L_p}$
44 Re_n net Reynolds number, $\rho U_n D / \mu$
45 Re_{osc} oscillatory Reynolds number, $\rho(2\pi f x_0) D / \mu$
46 Ψ velocity ratio, Re_{osc} / Re_n
47 Pr Prandtl number, $\mu c_p / k$
48 Nu Nusselt number, hD / k
49 Ra^* Modified Rayleigh number, $g \rho c_p \beta D^4 q'' / (\nu k^2)$

50 1. Introduction

51 The superposition of an oscillatory flow to a net flow
52 in a pipe is a well-known means for heat transfer en-
53 hancement [1, 2], driven by the increase in wall shear
54 stress and the potential change in flow direction. Heat
55 transfer characteristics of pulsating pipe flows have
56 been a focus of interest in a wide variety of applications,
57 ranging from turbomachinery cooling [3, 4, 5], cleaning
58 in place for food industry [6] or heat sinks for electron-
59 ics cooling [7], among others. A comprehensive review
60 of heat transfer enhancement by pulsating flows can be
61 found in [8].

62 When this active technique is combined with artifi-
63 cial tube roughness [9, 10] or with the use of inserts
64 [11], the resulting compound enhancement method pro-
65 vides a significant heat transfer augmentation, remark-
66 ably when low net flow velocities yield long residence
67 times in the pipe and laminar flow characteristics ex-
68 ist in the absence of pulsation. In particular, the super-
69 position of net and oscillatory flows in tubular baffled
70 reactors, as a means for achieving plug flow character-
71 istics [12], promotes also high tube-side heat transfer
72 coefficients, allowing to accommodate high heat fluxes

73 in chemical reactions that require simultaneous heat-
74 ing or cooling. Nusselt number correlations for the so-
75 called Oscillatory Baffled Reactors (OBRs) were pro-
76 posed for the first time by Mackley et al. [13], taking
77 into consideration the effect of the net flow velocity and
78 the frequency and amplitude of oscillation using the net
79 Reynolds number and the oscillatory Reynolds num-
80 ber. Single-orifice circular baffles were placed inside
81 the tube, allowing for the oscillatory flow to generate
82 a mechanism of cyclic dispersion of vortices upstream
83 and downstream of the periodically-spaced inserts, that
84 were responsible for the high degree of mixing, reduced
85 axial dispersion and heat transfer enhancement.

86 Table 1 collects the details (tested range and geom-
87 etry under study) of previous experimental studies on
88 thermal-hydraulic aspects of OBRs. Only studies with
89 oscillating flow (instead of oscillating baffles) are pre-
90 sented.

91 The scale-up of single-orifice OBRs, however,
92 showed a reduction of intensity and length-scale of mix-
93 ing. To overcome this problem, Smith and Mackley [26]
94 suggested the use of multi-orifice baffles, that would
95 mimic the many smaller diameter tubes in parallel pro-
96 posed by Ni [27] as a solution for the scaling-up of
97 single-orifice OBRs. This approach would be rather
98 similar to a reciprocating plate column [28], but oscil-
99 lating the fluid and not the baffles.

100 One distinctive feature of the multiorifice designs is
101 that they offer the option to rotate alternatively consec-
102 utive baffles, in order to break the strict flow periodic-
103 ity. This involves a modification of the flow structures,
104 in comparison with aligned multiorifice baffles. Heat
105 transfer performance, energy dissipation or radial mix-
106 ing might also be affected by this misalignment. How-
107 ever, while aligned baffles have been generally charac-
108 terized (flow behaviour [29], mixing [30], heat transfer
109 and pressure drop [22]), the effect of opposed multiorif-
110 ice baffles has rarely been treated in the open literature
111 [25]. In their publication, Baird and Rao [25] studied
112 the effect of the misalignment of multiorifice plates in
113 oscillatory baffled columns on power dissipation. They
114 found a significant influence of the misalignment for a
115 distance between plates $l = 50$ mm and oscillating am-
116 plitude $x_0 = 10$ mm, with $D = 190$ mm. The differ-
117 ences, however, were negligible for $x_0 = 5$ mm, as well
118 as for $l = 100$ mm and both amplitudes. The authors
119 did not provide any measurement uncertainty analysis,
120 which limits the significance of the results. The absence
121 of flow oscillation also limited the conclusions of this
122 work to the corpus of oscillatory baffled reactors. To
123 the best of our knowledge, no further investigations on
124 the misalignment of multiorifice plates in OBRs have
125 been reported so far in the open literature.

126 The lack of strict periodicity of the baffles' orienta-
127 tion in OBRs has been conversely studied from the per-
128 spective of different axial baffle arrangements. In their
129 search for the rupture of the shortcut between consec-
130 utive baffle orifices, Mazubert et al. [31] introduced

Table 1: Experimental studies on Oscillatory Baffled Reactors

Ref.	Type of test	Re_n	Re_{osc}	x_0/D	Pr	Geometry	$D(mm)$	l	S
[14]	FV, PD	0	300-4000	0.07-0.26	-	MH1	25.7	1.5D	0.35
[11]	HT	100-700	200-1600	0.12	124	MH1	12	1.5D	0.34
[13]	PD, HT	150-1000	300-800	0.29-0.57	72	MH1	12	1.5D	0.60
[15]	HT	0	50-1000	0.08-0.47	102	MH1	24	1.5D	0.16
[16]	FV	0	12-560	0.05-2.5	-	SPC	4.4	3D	0.13
[17]	FV	0	182-300	0.08	-	MH1	50	1.5D	0.25
[18]	HT	100-1000	0-1590	0.21	-	MH1	24	1.5D	-
[19]	FV	0	650-1300	4	-	MH3a	60	0.9D	0.24
[20]	HT	200-1400	0-2770	0.23	4.4-9	MH1	26.2	2D	0.25
[21]	HT	10-55	0-200	0.1-0.4	5.4	SPC	5	2.6D	0.16
[22]	PD, HT	10-600	10-440	0.5	190-470	MH3a	32	0.87D	0.25
[23]	FV, HT	20-65	0-650	0.5	150	MH1	32	1.5D	0.25
[24]	PD	0	10-1000	0.14-0.50	-	MH1, MH3a	32	1.5D	0.25
[25]	PD	0	$4 \cdot 10^3$ - $36 \cdot 10^3$	0.025-0.05	-	MH3a, MH3o	19.4	0.25D	0.169

Type of test: HT=Heat transfer, PD=Pressure drop, FV=Flow visualization

Geometry: MH1: one-orifice baffles, MH3a= three-orifice aligned baffles, MH3o= three-orifice opposed baffles

SPC=Smooth Periodic Constrictions

a central baffle between single-orifice baffles. The authors reported a significant increase in pressure drop and shear strain rate, but neither the axial dispersion nor the radial mixing were improved. Zhang et al. [32] evaluated different chambers connecting consecutive cells in oscillatory baffled crystallizers, with the aim of breaking the shortcut. They demonstrated the positive impact of these designs on the particle suspension performance of the reactor.

On the basis of this literature review, the impact of the misalignment of consecutive orifice baffles on the fluid mechanics and heat transfer performance of OBRs is still unclear. Most of the designs rely on the generation of jets across the orifices that yield vortex dispersion and further dissipation of the accelerated flow along each cell tank. Depending on the amplitude of the oscillation, a shortcut phenomenon might occur when jets cross aligned baffle orifices. The misalignment of consecutive orifice baffles, however, might involve different flow pattern mechanisms, whose description and influence on the friction and heat transfer characteristics of the flow have not been analysed.

In this work, a global approach to these open questions is applied to a tube with three-orifice baffles orientation with aligned and opposed configurations working under net, oscillatory and compound flow conditions. To this aim, three main measurement techniques are used in both a thermal-hydraulic and a visualization rig: (1) heat transfer tests to obtain the Nusselt number under uniform heat flux conditions and a Prandtl number of 65, (2) pressure drop tests under isothermal conditions to determine the net and oscillatory Fanning friction factors, and (3) PIV tests to derive the instantaneous velocity fields. The results are presented and discussed in different sections according to the type of

flow: net, oscillatory or compound. The dimensionless amplitude tested was the same for all the cases, $x_0/D = 0.5$, covering a wide range of Reynolds numbers: $50 < Re_n < 1000$ and $0 < Re_{osc} < 750$. The outcomes of this investigation allow us to establish the operational regions where opposed baffles can provide a significant enhancement over the aligned baffles.

2. Experimental methodology

2.1. Baffles tested

The baffles selected for the present investigation are depicted in Fig. 1 and will be abbreviated as MH3 baffles from this point forward. Three-circular orifices, $n_o = 3$, separated 120° provide the same open cross-section area than the standard orifice baffle, $S = 0.25$ (which was proposed as the optimum value by Ni et al. [12] from the results of mixing times for different operating conditions). The distance between baffles, l , is shorter if compared to one orifice baffles where $l = 1.5 \cdot D$, allowing for the appropriate dispersion of vortices along smaller cells. Following the recommendation from González-Juárez et al. [30], the ratio $l = 1.5 \cdot D_{eq}$ is kept constant, where $D_{eq} = D / \sqrt{n_o}$.

The baffles are made of PEEK plastic, to avoid electrical and thermal conduction from the tube wall, with thickness $e = 1$ mm.

Consecutive baffles present the same orientation with respect to the tube axis in the aligned baffle arrangement (Fig. 1a). Conversely, the opposed baffle arrangement (Fig. 1b) is built with a rotation of 60° between consecutive baffles.

Figure 1: Three-orifice baffles configurations tested: (a) aligned and (b) opposed.

2.2. PIV facility

The facility depicted in Fig. 2a was built for visualization purposes. The test section is made of acrylic tube with equally spaced inserted baffles. A total number of 12 baffles ensures the spatial periodicity of the flow field in its middle section. The test section is $L_v = 331$ mm long and complies with the dimensions in Fig. 3 with a wall thickness of 3 mm. The flow is visualized in the space between consecutive baffles. Around the visualization area, a flat-sided acrylic box, filled with the same working fluid, is placed to reduce optical distortion. Water is used as working fluid.

The temperature of the working fluid is adjusted using an electric heater (11) and a chiller (9) connected through a plate heat exchanger (8). A centrifugal pump (1) circulates the net flow from the reservoir tank (10) to the test section in a closed loop. The superposition of an oscillatory flow is achieved by the connection of a double-effect hydraulic cylinder (16) to the test section. The use of a slider-crank mechanism (15) allows for its activation, generating a sinusoidal linear displacement with frequencies between 0.12 Hz and 1.2 Hz. A flow control valve (2) is used to ensure a stable net flow. The position of the hydraulic cylinder (16) is measured by a magnetostrictive position sensor (17).

The flow is seeded with $57 \mu\text{m}$ polyamide particles with a density of 1051 kg/m^3 . A 1 mm thick laser light sheet of 808 nm wavelength illuminates a vertical plane of the tube. Consecutive images of the seeded flow are captured by a $1280 \times 1024 \text{ pix}^2$ CMOS IDT Motion-Scope M3 high speed camera. The spatial resolution of the images is around 0.031 mm. PIV is carried out by using PIVlab v2.31 for Matlab [33].

After PIV image pre-processing (background removal, histogram equalization, intensity high-pass and intensity capping), 97.7% of the velocity vectors are found valid, $PPR > 2$ (peak-to-peak ratio) for the net flow tests. Image processing is carried out by the adaptive FFT (Fast Fourier Transform) cross correla-

tion algorithm in four steps, with interrogation area sizes: $192 \times 192 \text{ pix}^2$, $128 \times 128 \text{ pix}^2$, $96 \times 96 \text{ pix}^2$ and $88 \times 88 \text{ pix}^2$ (all of them with a 50% overlap), leading to a spatial resolution of the velocity field equal to 1.35 mm. Post-processing includes the application of a global filter (based on the manual selection of the points that deviate significantly from the main cloud of points, when x and y velocity components are represented) and two local filters (based on the standard deviation and the median of the neighbour windows velocities).

Given the dissimilar velocities found both in the space and time domains, a time step between snapshots that ensured $PPR > 2$ for at least 85% of the velocity vectors at $\theta = 0^\circ$ (maximum average velocity) was chosen.

Table 2 summarizes the PIV tests carried out for both geometries and the time step between consecutive images that was used. This nomenclature (N1, N2, etc.) is also used along the paper to represent the tested points in the pressured drop and heat transfer results.

2.3. Thermohydraulic facility

Fig. 2b shows the thermohydraulic facility, where three different types of tests have been performed. The test section consists of a 2 meter long 316 stainless steel tube, with 32 mm i.d. and 1.5 mm wall thickness, where the baffles are introduced. The main tank (1) includes an electrical heater and mixer (13) that ensures a homogeneous mixture and heats the fluid when it is required. An external loop can keep constant the tank temperature in the range 15-40 °C.

Table 3 shows the values of the variables that have been modified to cover the tested ranges. The ranges tested were selected to reproduce conditions.

The flow rate range has been selected to reproduce the net Reynolds number range $50 < Re_n < 1000$ that: (1) covers the expected critical net Reynolds number (≈ 100 [22]) for the aligned baffles, so the differences between both configurations can be appreciated more clearly, and (2) there are potential applications, because a smooth tube would produce intense mixing at higher Reynolds numbers ($Re > 4000$).

The particularities for each type of test are described below.

2.3.1. Net pressure drop tests

The net pressure drop tests are carried out with valves (4) and (12) open, the oscillatory system (14-16) and transformer (10) are turned off, so there is only net flow (provided by the main pump (2)) and no heating is applied. These tests are performed under isothermal conditions at room temperature.

The net pressure drop is measured by a differential pressure transducer, model LD301 (8). Two different ranges are used for this study: 0-50 mbar and 0-500 mbar. The distance between pressure ports in the test section is 1295 mm, with 46 baffles located between them.

(a) PIV facility setup: (1) Centrifugal pump, (2) flow control valve, (3) input flow temperature probe B 1/10 DIN PT100, (4) test section with insert baffles and compensation box, (5) output flow temperature probe B 1/10 DIN PT100, (6) manual valve, (7) Coriolis flowmeter, (8) plate heat exchanger, (9) chiller, (10) reservoir tank, (11) electric heater with temperature control system, (12) PIV high speed camera equipped with a MACRO lens, (13) PIV laser, (14) motor-gear assembly, (15) rod-crank system, (16) double effect piston and (17) magnetostrictive position sensor.

(b) Thermohydraulic facility setup. (1) reservoir tank, (2) gear pump, (3) Coriolis flowmeter, (4 & 12) manual valves, (5 & 11) input/output temperature probes B 1/10 DIN PT100, (6) test section with insert baffles, (7) type T thermocouples set, (8) SMAR LD-301 static differential pressure sensors, (9) Kistler 4264A dynamic differential pressure sensors, (10) autotransformer, (13) agitator, (14) double effect hydraulic piston, (15) rod-crank assembly, (16) gear-motor group, (17) magnetostrictive position sensor

Figure 2: Experimental facilities.

Table 2: PIV tests data

Test	\dot{m} (kg/h)	x_0 (mm)	f (Hz)	Re_n	Re_{osc}	Δt (ms)
N1	10	-	0	115	0	20
N2	20	-	0	230	0	10
N3	30	-	0	460	0	5
O1	0	16	0.056	0	190	20
O2	0	16	0.112	0	380	6.7
O3	0	16	0.165	0	570	5
C1	10	16	0.056	115	190	20
C2	10	16	0.112	115	380	6.7
C3	10	16	0.165	115	570	5

Table 3: Thermohydraulic tests data (for both configurations)

Type of test	C (%)	T_b (°C)	\dot{m} (kg/h)	x_0 (mm)	f (Hz)	q'' (W/m ²)
Net pressure drop	50, 80	22	30-500	-	0	0
Oscillatory pressure drop	50, 80	22	0	16	0.22-2.2	0
Heat transfer	50	30*	30-500	16	0, 0.26, 0.66, 0.98, 1.30	5500-9000

*Bulk temperature measured at the first thermocouple section, $T_{b,1}$.

291 The fluid properties are evaluated at the mean tem- 323
 292 perature in the test section (PT100s (5) and (11)). Two 324
 293 propylene glycol-water mixtures, 50% and 80% propy- 325
 294 lene glycol, are used to widen the range of net Reynolds 326
 295 numbers covered and, at the system, check the repeata- 327
 296 bility of the measurements. 328

297 For each net Reynolds number tested, 100 samples 329
 298 are taken by the datalogger (model Agilent 34972A) at 330
 299 a frequency of 1 Hz. 331

300 2.3.2. Oscillatory pressure drop tests

301 For the oscillatory pressure drop tests, the main pump 332
 302 (2) is turned off and valves (4) and (12) are closed. The 333
 303 system is previously pressurized to avoid the potential 334
 304 risk of cavitation in the test section. Again, the trans- 335
 305 former is not connected, and the tests are performed at 336
 306 room temperature under isothermal conditions. 337

307 The flow takes place in the oscillatory loop, provided 338
 308 by the motion of a double-effect hydraulic cylinder (14). 339
 309 A crank and slider mechanism (15) ensures that it fol- 340
 310 lows a quasi-sinusoidal motion when it is connected to 341
 311 the motor (16). A magnetroctive sensor (17) measures 342
 312 the instantaneous position of the cylinder rod. 343

313 The instantaneous pressure drop between the pressure 344
 314 ports (the same used for the net pressure drop tests) is 345
 315 acquired by piezoresistive differential pressure sensors, 346
 316 model KISTLER 4264A, ranges ± 100 mbar and ± 1000 347
 317 mbar. These sensors have a response frequency of 2000 348
 318 Hz, enough to resolve the pressure drop signal for an 349
 319 oscillating cycle. 350

320 The high frequency signals (pressure drop and po- 351
 321 sition) are acquired by the acquisition card USB-6001 352
 322 (National instruments) at a sample rate of 2.8 kHz for 353

each channel. At least 20 oscillation cycles have been 354
 obtained for each oscillatory Reynolds number tested. 355

The fluid properties are evaluated at the mean tem- 356
 perature in the test section (from (5) and (11)). 357

To characterize the oscillatory pressure drop, the os- 358
 cillatory Fanning friction factor is calculated. It is based 359
 on the common definition of the Fanning friction factor, 360
 but using the maximum oscillatory velocity, $2\pi f x_0$, 361
 and the pressured drop amplitude, Δp_{max} , as the charac- 362
 teristic velocity and pressure drop, respectively. 363

$$364 f_{osc} = \frac{\Delta p_{max}}{2\rho(2\pi f x_0)^2} \frac{D}{L_p} \quad (1)$$

Δp_{max} , is obtained by a nonlinear statistical fitting (of 364
 the real pressured drop signal) to a sine wave. The value 365
 of the fitted amplitude is taken as Δp_{max} . 366

367 2.3.3. Heat transfer tests

368 The heat transfer tests are performed for net flow 369
 369 conditions and compound conditions (net + oscillatory 370
 370 flow). Thus, valves (4) and (12) are open and the heat- 371
 371 ing by Joule effect applied (10). The only difference 372
 372 between the tests for net flow and compound flow is the 373
 373 state of the oscillatory system (14-16), turned off or not, 374
 374 respectively. 375

The local Nusselt number at a given axial position is 376
 evaluated from: 377

$$378 Nu_j = \frac{V \cdot I - Q_{losses}}{\pi L_h (T_{wi,j} - T_{b,j})} \cdot \frac{1}{k_j} \quad (2)$$

379 V and I are the voltage and intensity applied by the 380
 380 transformer, their product corresponds to the raw heat 381
 381 applied to the tube. The voltage is measured directly 382

349 by the datalogger, while the intensity is measured by a 386
 350 hall effect sensor. L_h is the heated section length, which 387
 351 corresponds, for this case, to the distance between the 388
 352 two electrodes that connect the test section to the trans- 389
 353 former, $L_h = 1420$ mm. k_j is the thermal conductivity 390
 354 of the test fluid evaluated at the bulk temperature at the 391
 355 axial position j . It should be noted that the inner pipe 392
 356 wall is considered as the heat transfer surface area, due 393
 357 to the low thermal conductivity of the baffles. 394

358 $T_{b,j}$ is the fluid bulk temperature at the axial position 395
 359 j , which can be calculated as: 396

$$T_{b,j} = T_{b,in} + \frac{V \cdot I - Q_{losses}}{\dot{m} \cdot c_p} \cdot \frac{x_j}{L_h} \quad (3) \quad 397$$

360 Where $T_{b,in}$ is the inlet fluid temperature (from PT100 399
 361 (5)), \dot{m} is the mass flow rate (Coriolis flow meter (3)), 400
 362 and c_p is the specific heat of the fluid at the inlet tem- 401
 363 perature. x_j is the distance between the axial position j 402
 364 and the start of the heated section. 403

365 The inner wall temperature cannot be measured directly, 404
 366 so the outer wall temperature is taken instead by type T 405
 367 thermocouples (7). For each axial position j , 8 thermocouples 406
 368 equally distributed are placed on the outer wall of the tube 407
 369 as depicted in Fig. 3 (ensuring an accurate measurement 408
 370 when flow stratification is present). The average of these 8 409
 371 measurements is taken as the outer wall temperature. To derive 410
 372 the inner wall temperature from the outer, a 1D discrete model 411
 373 is used to solve the heat conduction with internal heat gener- 412
 374 ation in the tube. 413
 375

Figure 3: Dimensions of the baffles and thermocouple disposition (red 428
 429 dots) for aligned (a) and opposed (b) baffles. 430

376 The heat losses, Q_{losses} , are estimated from the aver- 431
 377 aged outer wall temperature, by considering the thermal 432
 378 conductivity and thickness of the thermal insulation 433
 379 layer and the outer heat transfer coefficient (natural convec- 434
 380 tion) from well-known correlations for a horizontal cylinder 435
 381 [34]. The tube was thermally insulated 436
 382 with a layer of rockwool (thermal conductivity of 0.035 437
 383 W/(m·K)) with a thickness of 50 mm. The outer surface 438
 384 was covered with a 5 mm thick multilayer insulation 439
 385 (aluminium and polyethylene) of low emissivity (0.06). 440

386 These calculations are repeated for 8 axial sections 387
 388 to catch the variability of the Nusselt number along one 389
 390 cell (distance between baffles), which is due to the fact 391
 392 that the baffles prevent the flow development. Because 393
 394 one cell length is too short to place 8 measurement sec- 395
 396 tions (64 thermocouples in total), the periodicity of the 397
 398 flow is considered to place the measuring section in 8
 399 different cell positions (relative to the previous baffle)
 400 and different cells.

401 For all the signals, 30 samples for each test are ac-
 402 quired by two dataloggers (model Agilent 34970A and
 403 34972A), with an acquisition rate of 0.1 Hz.

2.4. Fluid properties

404 The required fluid properties (density, dynamic vis-
 405 cosity, specific heat and thermal conductivity) are
 406 calculated by interpolation on the tabulated data
 407 of propylene-glycol and water mixtures included in
 408 ASHRAE's 2001 fundamentals book [35], as a function
 409 of the temperature and the propylene-glycol concentra-
 410 tion.

411 Because the propylene-glycol concentration is sensi-
 412 tive to previous tests (dead zones in the hydraulic cir-
 413 cuit) and the humidity in the lab (propylene-glycol is
 414 hygroscopic), it is important to consider a method to
 415 periodically measure the real concentration. To do so,
 416 a Cannon-Fenske viscometer is used to measure the kin-
 417 ematic viscosity in a thermostatic bath at a known tem-
 418 perature (around 30 °C), then the concentration that bet-
 419 ter fits the measured viscosity is considered. The high
 420 sensitivity of the fluid viscosity with the concentration
 421 provides a low uncertainty.

2.5. Uncertainty analysis

422 The uncertainty analysis follows the methodology in-
 423 cluded in [36]. As a sum up, the uncertainty of each
 424 direct measurement (e.g., net pressure drop) includes
 425 the bias component (obtained from the sensor manufac-
 426 turer, collected in Table 4) and the random component
 427 (derived from the standard deviation of the correspond-
 428 ing measurements of a variable); then, error propaga-
 429 tion is applied to calculate the global uncertainty of
 430 the variables of interest (e.g., net friction factor).

431 As can be observed, the fluid properties uncertain-
 432 ties are not included in Table 4, because these are not
 433 a variable directly measured, but derived from the con-
 434 centration and temperature of the fluid. Consequently,
 435 they are calculated for each tested by applying the er-
 436 ror propagation (from the uncertainties of the fluid tem-
 437 perature and concentration). Because the properties are
 438 derived from interpolation on tabulated data, the partial
 439 derivatives to apply the error propagation formula were
 440 obtained numerically.

441 The uncertainty for each test for a 95% confidence
 442 interval is included directly in all the figures through-
 443 out this work. Table 5 shows the maximum and average
 444 uncertainty for the different results of interest.

Table 4: Measurement uncertainties

Measurement	Uncertainty
Mixture concentration, C	0.7%
Tube diameter, D	0.1% measure
Heat transfer section, L_h	0.01 m
Thermocouples position, x_j	0.005 m
Pressure test length, L_p	0.005 m
Mass flow rate, \dot{m}	0.2% measure
Net pressure drop, Δp_n	0.1% full scale (50 or 500 mbar)
Frequency, f	0.004 Hz
Oscillation amplitude, x_0	0.3 mm
Oscillatory pressure drop, Δp_{max}	0.2% full scale (100 mbar or 1 bar)
Inlet temperature, $T_{b,in}$	$0.1 \cdot (0.03 + 0.005 \cdot T(^{\circ}C))$
Outer wall temperature, T_{we}	1.0 $^{\circ}C$
Voltage, V	0.06% measure + 0.04% full scale (10 V)
Intensity, I	2% full scale (600 A)
Heat losses, Q_{losses}	50% measure

Table 5: Uncertainties of the relevant variables

Variable	Max. uncertainty	Mean uncertainty
Re_n	5.8%	2.2%
Re_{osc}	5.7%	3.8%
x_0/D	1.8%	1.8%
Pr	3.4%	1.9%
Ra^*	4.7%	3.5%
f_n	15.1	4.2%
f_{osc}	16.0%	5.7%
Nu	10.2%	6.9%

3. Results

3.1. Net flow

Pressure drop. Fig. 4 shows the Fanning friction factor under net flow conditions for both the aligned and the opposed three orifice baffles. The results for the opposed baffles are obtained for two different propylene glycol-water mixtures to increase the range of net Reynolds numbers tested and to prove the consistence of the results where the ranges for both mixtures overlap ($Re_n = 50 - 300$).

At low net Reynolds numbers, $Re_n < 40$, both configurations display the same trend and differences below the experimental uncertainty. However, the opposed baffles experience a sharp change in the curve slope at $Re_n \approx 40$, indicating the end of the laminar flow regime, while the aligned baffles show a similar behaviour at $Re_n \approx 90$. Thus, both configurations imply a significant reduction in the critical net Reynolds number when compared to one-orifice baffles, where $Re_n \approx 165$ [37].

The transition occurs smoothly when compared to a smooth tube, and the trends are different enough to prevent the use of one of the available methods to delimit the different flow regimes [38].

Beyond the laminar flow region, the friction factor is significantly higher for the opposed baffles, a maximum

of 60% for N1 ($Re_n = 115$), and around 40% in the region where the friction factor for both configurations seems to become stable (N3).

Figure 4: Net Fanning friction factor vs net Reynolds number for both MH3 baffle types.

Velocity field. The velocity field in pure net flow conditions has been obtained in a symmetry plane of the tube at $Re_n = 115$ (N1) and $Re_n = 460$ (N3) for both configurations. The analysis in these operational conditions is aimed at helping to identify the smooth transition to turbulence observed in pressure drop results (Fig. 4).

As shown in Fig. 5a and Fig. 7a, for $Re_n = 115$ and $Re_n = 460$, respectively, the average flow pattern for the aligned geometry is dominated by a jet connecting the orifices of consecutive baffles and a recirculation bubble that extends along the upper half of the cell. (Fig. 7a). Increasing the net Reynolds number results in lower velocities in the final part of the jet (Fig. 7a-I), presumably due to higher momentum diffusivity, and higher local velocities in the recirculation bubble (Fig. 7a-II).

The average velocity field depicted in Fig. 5b and Fig. 7b for the opposed baffles' arrangement allows us to observe a similar jet structure downstream of the baf-

fles. However, the misalignment of the baffle located immediately downstream prevents the further development of the jet. The recirculation in the upper part of the cell is affected by the three-dimensional flow structures originated by the blockage encountered by the jet. Local axial velocities in the visualization plane are higher than radial velocities. The evacuation of the flow through the upper orifice of the baffle downstream (Fig. 5b-I) is also detected. The increase of the net Reynolds number causes the jet to dissipate faster, being significantly shorter for $Re_n = 460$ than for $Re_n = 115$.

As shown in pressure drop experiments for both configurations, the flow presents a smooth transition to turbulence. A good measure for the flow instability is to compare average and instantaneous velocity fields. When doing so at $Re_n = 115$ (Fig. 5), small differences are observed for the aligned geometry, while the differences are more clearly detected for the opposed geometry. In any case, the flow does not show fully turbulent characteristics, although these results and pressure drop ones imply that the flow is, at least, transitional for both geometries.

The comparison of average and instantaneous velocity fields at $Re_n = 460$ (Fig. 7) confirms, for both geometries, the chaotic nature of the flow. These observations can be quantified by performing a Proper Orthogonal Decomposition analysis [39] that decomposes the flow in a series of coherent structures (modes) arranged by its corresponding kinetic energy. The first mode corresponds to the averaged velocity field and, consequently, the kinetic energy of the averaged field can be compared to the total kinetic energy of the flow (averaged plus fluctuations) in order to evaluate the weight of the fluctuations.

Fig. 6 represents the kinetic energy of the fluctuating components (as a percentage of the total kinetic energy of the flow) as a function of the net Reynolds number. Even at the lower net Reynolds number, $Re_n = 110$, the fluctuating components have a significant weight on the energy of the flow for both configurations, $> 5\%$. It should be considered that the flow may present fluctuations even under laminar flow conditions due to: measurement uncertainties, fluctuations of the flow rate due to the pump, etc. As a reference, a 2% of the kinetic energy of the fluctuations was measured for a laminar case in a one-orifice baffle configuration under similar working conditions (lighting, particle size, PIV algorithm, etc.) [40].

The effect of increasing the net Reynolds numbers is clear for both geometries: an increase on the kinetic energy of the fluctuations. For the range of net Reynolds numbers tested, the weight of the fluctuations is higher for the opposed baffles (around 3-5%), which confirms the more 'chaotic' behavior observed for this configuration.

Additionally, a better understanding of the instantaneous flow field characteristics for both geometries and the experiments N1 to N3 can be obtained from Video 1,

where compositions of PIV instantaneous velocity fields are shown and analysed.

In contrast with the flow structures reported in one-orifice baffled tubes, low velocity regions do not appear downstream of each orifice in any of the configurations analysed. The recirculations close to the tube wall are not detected either, and this kind of structure is only found in the spaces opposed to each one of the orifices. This observation was already reproduced numerically by González-Juárez et al. [30] for oscillatory flow conditions.

Heat transfer. Fig. 8a shows the Nusselt number as a function of the net Reynolds number for both baffle orientations and a Prandtl number $Pr = 65$. Only one propylene-glycol water mixture has been used, reducing the range tested in comparison to the pressure drop measurements. Rayleigh number in the range $Ra^* = 1.5 - 3.2 \cdot 10^8$ has been tested; for the sake of a better comparison, the value is approximately the same for both baffle orientations at each net Reynolds number.

As a reference, the dashed lines represent the values obtained from correlations for MH3 aligned baffles, available in a previous study [22]. In the laminar flow regime, the experimental results overlap with the correlation, while the experimental data in the turbulent region falls below the correlation ($\sim 10\%$). This mismatch is acceptable if we consider the uncertainty associated to the correlation, and the fact that it was developed for the range $190 < Pr < 470$, far from the value used in this study ($Pr = 65$).

As can be seen, there is no variation in the curve slope for the range tested for the opposed baffles, confirming that no relevant flow transition takes place. In fact, all the data can be fitted to the correlation in Eq. 4 with a deviation lower than 10%. On the other hand, the aligned baffles show a sharp increase on the Nusselt number at $Re_n = 130$, indicating the end of laminar flow regime. This value is close to the critical Reynolds number, $Re_n = 105$, obtained by Muñoz-Cámara et al. [22].

$$Nu_{op} = 0.412 \cdot Re_n^{0.757} \cdot Pr^{0.285} \quad (4)$$

It is the range from the end of the laminar region of the opposed baffles to the end of the laminar region of the aligned, $Re_n = 40 - 130$, where there is a noticeable heat transfer enhancement. A maximum increase of 27% in the Nusselt number is achieved at $Re_n = 120$. For $Re_n > 150$, the enhancement falls below the experimental uncertainty.

The different value for the critical net Reynolds number from the pressure drop results, $Re_n = 90$, and the heat transfer results, $Re_n = 130$, can be partly explained by the measurement uncertainty. But another relevant factor could be the thermal effects associated to the heat transfer tests: presence of mixed convection and wall-fluid temperature drop.

Figure 5: PIV velocity fields at $Re_n = 115$ for the geometries under study. Experiment N1 (Table 2).

Figure 6: Energy of the fluctuating components of the flow, from a Proper Orthogonal Decomposition analysis, as a function of the net Reynolds number

599 The existence of buoyancy effects on the flow can
600 be deduced from local wall temperature measurements.
601 As an example, the average temperature difference (for
602 the 8 axial positions) between the upper and lower thermocouples is plotted in Fig. 8b as a function of the net Reynolds number.
603
604

605 Both baffle orientations display a high vertical temperature gradient at low net Reynolds numbers. The aligned baffles show the expected behaviour: temperature stratification (i.e., natural convection effects) in the laminar region ($Re_n < 130$) and negligible stratification in the transitional-turbulent regions. On the contrary, the opposed baffles should not experience a flow transition in the tested range, but they also display a significantly high temperature stratification, but lower than the aligned baffles. Thus, it can be concluded that the opposed baffles are working under turbulent or transitional mixed convection conditions for $Re_n < 130$.
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617 If the values for both configurations are compared,
618 the opposed baffles display a significantly lower temperature stratification for all the range tested below $Re_n = 130$, for example, for N1 ($Re_n = 115$) the temperature difference is 15 °C lower for the opposed baffles. For higher net Reynolds numbers (for example points N2 and N3) the temperature stratification is negligible for both configurations.
621
622
623
624

625 There is a change in the decreasing trend of the temperature stratification as a function of the net Reynolds number, which cannot be explained by the measurement
626
627

Figure 7: PIV velocity fields at $Re_n = 460$ for the geometries under study. Experiment N3 (Table 2).

628 uncertainty. The increase in the temperature difference
 629 between $Re_n = 70$ and $Re_n = 80$ is due to the in-
 630 crease of the Rayleigh number from $Ra^* = 1.6 \cdot 10^7$
 631 to $Ra^* = 2.2 \cdot 10^7$. While the Rayleigh number was
 632 kept constant for the three lowest net Reynolds num-
 633 bers, it was modified for the next point to keep a high
 634 enough wall-fluid temperature to ensure an acceptable
 635 uncertainty for the Nusselt number.

636 3.2. Oscillatory flow

637 The oscillatory flow has been studied by performing
 638 pressure drop and visualization tests.

639 *Pressure drop.* Fig. 9 shows the oscillatory Fanning
 640 friction factor as a function of the oscillatory Reynolds
 641 number for a dimensionless amplitude $x_0/D = 0.5$. The
 642 oscillatory friction factor for the opposed baffles' con-
 643 figuration does not show any sharp change on its trend,
 644 indicating that there is no flow regime transition in the
 645 studied range, or it is quite smooth. For the aligned baf-
 646 fles' arrangement, friction reaches a minimum at around
 647 $Re_{osc} \approx 200$ (near O1), which could correspond to the
 648 end of the unsteady laminar region. The friction fac-
 649 tor is again significantly higher for the opposed baffles'
 650 configuration, around 20% for $Re_{osc} = 570$ (test O3).

651 As a reference, results from the correlation proposed
 652 by Muñoz-Cámara et al. [24], which provides the oscil-
 653 latory friction factor as a function of Re_{osc} and x_0/D , is
 654 plotted. For $Re_{osc} < 300$, there is a good match between
 655 the experimental results and the correlation. However,

656 the correlation underestimates the friction factor at high
 657 Re_{osc} , what could be due to: (1) the correlation was
 658 developed for $0.14 < x_0/D < 0.43$ while the value
 659 $x_0/D = 0.5$ was used for this study, and (2) the rela-
 660 tive lack of points at high Re_{osc} that were available to
 661 develop the correlation. Regarding the opposed baffles,
 662 the data seems to approach the aligned baffles curve at
 663 low Re_{osc} , as it happens for net flow conditions, however
 664 the minimum Re_{osc} tested is not low enough to confirm
 665 this point.

666 The data for the opposed MH3 baffles can be fitted to
 667 the following correlation within a 5% deviation:

$$f_{osc,op} = \frac{70.1}{Re_{osc}} + 7.32 \cdot Re_{osc}^{-0.0327}, x_0/D = 0.53 \quad (5)$$

668 The uncertainty associated to the experimental mea-
 669 surements is high, and it is mainly due to the pressure
 670 transducer uncertainty. However, the real uncertainty is
 671 expected to be lower due to the fact that the differential
 672 pressure transducer measures the amplitude of the pres-
 673 sure drop (i.e., the difference between the pressure drop
 674 during the positive and negative half-cycles), instead of
 675 an 'absolute' pressure; this implies that the bias compo-
 676 nent of the sensor error would have a lower effect on the
 677 measurement error than the one that was considered.

678 *Velocity field.* The oscillatory flow field is presented for
 679 both configurations and $Re_{osc} = 190$ (O1) and $Re_{osc} =$
 680 570 (O3) in Fig. 11 and Fig. 12, respectively. The flow

Figure 8: (a) Nusselt number and (b) temperature stratification vs net Reynolds number for both MH3 baffle orientations, $Pr = 65$ ($C=50\%$).

Figure 9: Oscillatory Fanning friction factor vs oscillatory Reynolds number for both MH3 baffle orientations. $x_0/D = 0.5$

681 pattern of the experiments is shown for different po-
 682 sitions of the oscillatory cycle, which is presented in
 683 terms of θ , the cycle position, as illustrated in Fig. 10.
 684 The value $\theta = 0^\circ$ corresponds to the instant of maximum
 685 average velocity towards the right side.

Figure 10: Phases of the oscillation cycle for flow field representation (PIV technique).

686 The oscillatory flow is symmetric in time, meaning
 687 that the flow between $0^\circ < \theta < 180^\circ$ is symmetric to
 688 the one between $180^\circ < \theta < 360^\circ$. Being so, results are
 689 presented for $\theta = 0^\circ, 45^\circ, 90^\circ, 135^\circ$. The results for
 690 $Re_{osc} = 190$ at $\theta = 0^\circ$ (maximum averaged velocity)
 691 in the aligned geometry (Fig. 11a), show a phase-average
 692 velocity field which is very similar to the one of the net
 693 flow: a jet connects consecutive baffles orifices and a
 694 recirculation is present in the opposed flow region. At
 695 $\theta = 90^\circ$, when the average velocity equals zero, the flow
 696 pattern is still governed by the jet due to the inertia of
 697 the flow (Fig. 11a-I). Later in the cycle, at $\theta = 135^\circ$,
 698 the previous jet has vanished, and a new jet is formed at
 699 the right baffle (Fig. 11a-II).

700 For the opposed baffle geometry, the results show
 701 similar trends (Fig. 11b), beginning at $\theta = 0^\circ$ with a pat-
 702 tern similar to the one obtained for the net flow test, with
 703 a jet in the direction of the flow which loses strength and
 704 at $\theta = 90^\circ$ is part of a recirculation which fully covers
 705 the inter-baffle space. At $\theta = 135^\circ$, a new jet takes shape
 706 in the opposite direction, from the baffle orifice at the
 707 right-hand side of the picture.

708 The videos (for points O1, O2 and O3 and both con-
 709 figuration) support the trend of the pressure drop results:
 710 the friction factor is deviated from the laminar trend for
 711 $Re_{osc} > 200$ and, at the same time, the instantaneous ve-
 712 locity fields along one oscillation cycle display a more
 713 chaotic behaviour with the jet deviating from its direc-
 714 tion and fluctuating.

715 PIV phase-average velocity fields for $Re_{osc} = 570$
 716 are shown in Fig. 12. When compared with results for
 717 $Re_{osc} = 190$, the increase in the oscillatory Reynolds
 718 number implies an increase of momentum diffusivity.

Figure 11: Phase-average pure oscillatory flow field at $Re_{osc} = 190$ for both geometries and different cycle positions. Experiment O1 (Table 2).

719 Other than that, the non-dimensional average velocity 743
720 fields are similar for both working conditions. 744

721 The oscillatory Reynolds number tested, $Re_{osc} = 570$, 745
722 is very close to that studied by Nogueira et al. [19] for 746
723 aligned baffles. While the amplitude they tested was 747
724 low, $x_0/D = 0.045$, in comparison to the value used 748
725 in this study, $x_0/D = 0.5$, they also observed a three- 749
726 dimensional and very complex flow for $Re_{osc} = 600$, 750
727 which was dominated by eddy formation, as can be also 751
728 observed in the video for the test O3 (aligned configura- 752
729 tion). 753

730 3.3. Compound flow 755

731 In this section, the superposition of net and oscillatory 756
732 flows is studied using visualization and heat trans- 757
733 fer experiments. In order to quantify their relative im- 758
734 portance, the velocity ratio is defined as follows: 759

$$760 \Psi = \frac{Re_{osc}}{Re_n} \quad (6) \quad 761$$

735 *Velocity field.* PIV experiments have been carried out 764
736 for a fixed net Reynolds number of $Re_n = 115$ and an 765
737 oscillatory Reynolds number which varies within the 766
738 range $Re_{osc} = 190 - 570$, resulting in a velocity ratio 767
739 within $\Psi = 1.7 - 5.0$. 768

740 Fig. 13 shows the phase-averaged velocity field for 769
741 both aligned and opposed baffles arrangements at $\Psi =$ 770
742 1.7 (C1). In this case, the net flow bulk velocity is lower 771

743 than the maximum oscillatory flow bulk velocity. This 744
745 results in a change of direction of the compound flow. In 746
747 the figure, the net flow goes rightwards. The result for 748
749 both geometries is that the flow is still dominated by the 750
751 net flow direction, with flow reversal (Fig. 13a-I) taking 752
753 place for a small fraction of the cycle $\theta = 180^\circ - 225^\circ$. 754

755 As before, with regard to convection mechanisms, we 756
757 observe recirculations at almost any cycle position, im- 758
759 proving the radial mixing. Flow circulation in radial di- 760
761 rection is relatively more important at positions where 762
763 a change of flow direction occurs (at $\theta = 135^\circ, 270^\circ$), 764
765 proving that flow reversal is critical to achieve a good 766
767 mixing when there is a net flow. 768

769 The increase of the relative importance of the oscillatory 770
771 flow up to a velocity ratio $\Psi = 5$ (C3) results in an 772
773 increase of the fraction of the cycle with a reverse flow. 774
775 Thus, the importance of the net flow is significantly re- 776
777 duced, and the results presented in Fig. 14 show very 778
779 similar flow patterns to the ones of a pure oscillatory 779
780 flow (Fig. 12). However, the effect of the net flow is 780
781 still noticeable, for example, at $\theta = 90^\circ$ the jet formed 781
782 in the orifice is stronger than that of the oscillatory flow, 782
783 or at $\theta = 135^\circ$, the jet in opposite direction is weaker 783
784 in comparison to the oscillatory flow case. 784

785 The only study available in the open literature for 786
787 aligned three-orifice baffles under compound flow condi- 787
788 tions was performed by González-Juárez et al. [30], 788
789 where they simulated a flow with $Re_n = 50$ and $Re_{osc} =$ 789
790 800 , for an amplitude $x_0/D = 0.3$. The authors observed 790
791

Figure 12: Phase-average pure oscillatory flow field at $Re_{osc} = 570$ for both geometries and different cycle positions. Experiment O3 (Table 2).

772 a highly chaotic flow and vigorous mixing, which is
 773 consistent with the measured velocity fields at $Re_n =$
 774 115 and $Re_{osc} = 570$ (see video of the test C3, aligned
 775 configuration), when the flow already displays similar
 776 characteristics.

777 **Heat transfer.** Fig.15 a-b show the Nusselt number as a
 778 function of the net Reynolds number for both baffle ori-
 779 entations, and different oscillatory Reynolds numbers.
 780 The dimensionless amplitude is identical to that used
 781 for the pure oscillatory flow tests ($x_0/D = 0.5$). For the
 782 sake of comparison, the Prandtl number, the Rayleigh
 783 number and the oscillatory Reynolds number for each
 784 test are kept almost identical for both baffles ori-
 785 entations.

786 The effect of the net Reynolds number on the Nus-
 787 selt is noticeable even at low net Reynolds numbers
 788 and high oscillatory Reynolds numbers (high velocity
 789 ratios). This implies that the net component has an
 790 important role on the heat transfer process and cannot
 791 be neglected even for the highest velocity ratios tested
 792 ($\Psi \approx 15$). This is supported by the flow patterns pre-
 793 viously observed (Fig. 13 and 14), where the net flow
 794 show a strong influence on the flow for low and high
 795 velocity ratios.

796 The oscillatory Reynolds number has also a positive
 797 effect on the heat transfer enhancement, e.g., a maximun
 798 increase of 100% on the Nusselt number is observed at
 799 $Re_n = 50$ when the oscillatory Reynolds number is in-

800 creased from 150 to 760. The trend can also be clearly
 801 observed if we follow the values of the PIV tests: for
 802 C1 ($Re_n = 115$, $Re_{osc} = 190$) $Nu \approx 50$, while for C3
 803 ($Re_n = 115$, $Re_{osc} = 570$) $Nu \approx 100$. However, all
 804 the curves overlap when the magnitude of the net and
 805 oscillatory Reynolds numbers is similar.

806 These trends can be presented more clearly if the data
 807 for the opposed baffles is fitted to a correlation with the
 808 following form:

$$Nu_{op} = 0.385 \cdot Re_n^{0.338} \cdot Re_{osc}^{0.435} \cdot Pr^{0.285}, \Psi > 1 \quad (7)$$

809 where the data with $\Psi < 1$ has not been considered
 810 because they follow the trend of the net flow tests.

811 In general, if baffle orientations are compared, the
 812 trends are almost identical for the four frequencies
 813 tested. In addition, while the opposed baffles provide
 814 consistently higher Nusselt number for all the range
 815 tested, the heat transfer enhancement is moderate and
 816 falls below the measurement uncertainty. Only for the
 817 lowest frequency tested ($Re_{osc} = 145 - 150$), and low
 818 net Reynolds numbers ($Re_n < 150$) there is a noticeable
 819 heat transfer enhancement (around 20% at $Re_n = 55$,
 820 but this value falls to a 10% at $Re_n = 250$).

821 The effect of the oscillatory flow can also be observed
 822 on the temperature stratification, as shown in Fig. 16,
 823 where the upper-lower local wall temperature difference
 824 is plotted for both orientations at the lowest oscillatory

Figure 13: Phase-average compound flow field at $Re_n = 115$ (flowing rightwards) and $\Psi = 1.7$ for both geometries and different cycle positions. Experiment C1 (Table 2).

(a) Aligned baffle arrangement.

(b) Opposed baffle arrangement.

Figure 14: Phase-average compound flow field at $Re_n = 115$ (flowing rightwards), $\Psi = 5$ for both geometries and different cycle positions. Experiment C3 (Table 2).

(a) $Re_{osc} \approx 150, 560$

(b) $Re_{osc} \approx 380, 750$

Figure 15: Nusselt number vs net Reynolds number for different oscillatory Reynolds numbers and both MH3 baffle orientations.

825 Reynolds number tested, $Re_{osc} \approx 150$. For the aligned
 826 baffles, the temperature difference at low Re_n is reduced
 827 up to a 70%, from 30°C to 8 °C at $Re_n = 60$, while
 828 for the opposed baffles the stratification is almost negli-
 829 gible for all the Re_n range tested, supporting what was
 830 observed for net flow tests: the opposed baffles reduce
 831 significantly the temperature stratification when compared
 832 to the aligned. For both orientations, at higher
 833 oscillatory Reynolds numbers, the stratification is non-
 834 existent.

Figure 16: Temperature stratification vs net Reynolds number for both MH3 baffle orientations.

835 4. Conclusions

836 A systematic experimental analysis in a three-orifice
 837 oscillatory baffled tube has allowed to establish the ef-
 838 fect of opposing consecutive baffles in their friction,
 839 heat transfer and flow pattern characteristics. The main
 840 conclusions derived from this work are:

- 841 • For net flow: opposed baffles increase the friction
 842 factor up to 40 % in the range $40 < Re_n < 1000$,
 843 while heat transfer is only increased up to 27 %
 844 in the range $50 < Re_n < 150$. This augmentation
 845 is caused by the earlier transition to turbulence re-
 846 duction of the critical Reynolds number when the
 847 baffles are opposed, from $Ren \approx 100$ to $Ren \approx 40$.
 848 The visualization tests shows a more chaotic be-
 849 haviour for the opposed baffles at low net Reynolds
 850 numbers.
- 851 • For oscillatory flow: opposed baffles display a
 852 maximum increase of the oscillatory friction fac-
 853 tor of 20 % in comparison to the aligned baffles.
 854 Apparently, the deviation from the expected lam-
 855 inar trend for the opposed baffles takes place at
 856 a lower oscillatory Reynolds number. More tests for
 857 $Re_{osc} < 50$ should be performed to prove this point.
- 858 • For compound flow, both baffle orientations show
 859 a remarkable effect of the oscillatory flow on the
 860 Nusselt number, up to a 100% increase at the lower
 861 net Reynolds number tested, $Re_n = 50$. However,

there are only noticeable differences between both orientations at low Reynolds numbers: $Re_{osc} < 150$ and $Re_n < 150$.

- The study of the temperature stratification have shown that the opposed baffles reduce its effect (more uniform temperature distribution) for the range in which it appears, $Re_{osc} \leq 150$ and $Re_n < 200$. The stratification is negligible for higher Reynolds numbers.

For only net flow applications, due to the significant increase in the pressure drop, both configurations are suitable for applications that would require to work in laminar or transitional conditions for a smooth tube ($Re_n < 4000$) when baffles can provide a remarkable heat transfer enhancement. This is typically the case for viscous fluids that require low flow velocities to reduce the overall pressure drop, as those that can be found in chemical, petrochemical or food industries.

The pure oscillatory flow applications are generally limited to cases where the baffles can provide a benefit in comparison to stirred tanks, e.g., a lower shear rate, that would be desirable for an algae bioreactor.

The compound oscillatory flow applications include any process that require a high residence time (chemical reaction), what would lead to low net flow velocities and very low Reynolds numbers in a smooth tube.

For the opposed baffles specifically, these can be recommended under net flow conditions for low net Reynolds numbers, $Re_n < 150$. The same can be stated for compound flow: low oscillatory and net Reynolds numbers, $Re_{osc} < 150$ and $Re_n < 150$. From the point of view of the mixing performance, the observed flow patterns seem to point out a noticeable difference. Thus, it would be interesting to complement this study with techniques to measure the axial dispersion, where the opposed baffles can still be expected to produce an improvement.

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